

Evaluating Tall Pier Bridge Systems: Analysis, Design Methodologies, and Economic Consequences

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ABSTRACT- This paper provides a comprehensive methodology for analyzing, designing, and evaluating the cost of reinforced concrete tall bridge piers with various cross-sections and their foundations. The study focuses on deep valley bridge viaducts where pier heights are typically between 30 and 100 meters. The design charts generated in this study aid in the preliminary design of tall pier bridges under seismic loading. The study also considers different concrete grades, such as M40, M50, M60, and M70. The other cards in the deck cover topics such as pile foundation for bridges, methodology and bridge parameters, loads and load combinations, analysis results and cost comparison, optimum pier and foundation design, seismic performance and design considerations, construction techniques and challenges, maintenance and durability considerations, future research, and emerging trends.

Keywords: High pier; Non-linear method; RC bridge; Seismic condition; Time-history analysis; 3D modelling.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past two decades, there has been remarkable progress in the field of concrete bridge engineering, including advancements in structural design, the emergence of new construction methods, and the development of high-strength materials [1]. However, there has been a recognized need for standardized design methodologies for bridges, particularly in India, aligning with international standards and utilizing the limit state approach.

Concrete bridges, especially those spanning mountainous terrain, present unique challenges due to variable pier heights. The seismic response of such bridges is significantly influenced by both their geometry and the characteristics of the piers [2]. During an earthquake, the interaction between tall and short piers complicates the forces acting on the bridge structure [3].

Earthquakes, characterized by sudden and intense ground shaking, pose significant threats and are considered one of the most devastating natural disasters [4]. Therefore, it's imperative to design structures with a comprehensive understanding of seismic behavior. Structural engineers have various options at their disposal to devise systems that not only meet architectural requirements but also withstand seismic forces effectively.

II. PILE FOUNDATION

Pile foundations are an increasingly popular choice for bridges, offering several advantages over traditional well foundations [5]. They enable faster construction, reduce time overruns, and are more economical, especially for large-span bridges (Figure 1). Pile foundations are particularly suitable in scenarios where deep foundations are required, such as in areas with deep soil layers prone to scour or where the upper soil layers are highly compressible and unable to support the superstructure load.

Figure 1 pile foundation for bridges

BORED CAST-IN-SITU PILES

Bored cast-in-situ piles are a widely used type of pile foundation for bridges. These piles offer several advantages over other types of foundation systems, making them a popular choice among engineers and contractors [6].

The construction process of bored cast-in-situ piles involves the drilling of a borehole using a chisel or auger. During the drilling process, bentonite slurry is used to stabilize the borehole and prevent it from collapsing. This slurry also helps in removing the excavated soil from the borehole.

Once the desired depth is reached, a reinforcement cage is lowered into the borehole [7]. The reinforcement cage provides additional strength and stability to the pile. After the cage is properly positioned, concrete is poured into the borehole using a tremie pipe. The tremie pipe ensures that the concrete is placed at the bottom of the borehole without any segregation or displacement.

Bored cast-in-situ piles are known for their ability to withstand heavy loads and provide excellent stability even in challenging soil conditions. They are particularly suitable for bridge foundations where the soil layers are deep, prone to scour, or have low bearing capacity [8].

One of the key advantages of bored cast-in-situ piles is their versatility. They can be installed in a variety of soil types, including clay, sand, and rock. The diameter of the pile can be adjusted based on the load requirements and soil conditions, allowing for optimal design and cost-effectiveness (Figure 2).

In addition to their versatility, bored cast-in-situ piles offer other benefits such as faster construction, reduced time overruns, and improved cost-effectiveness. The construction process can be efficiently carried out using standard equipment and techniques, making it a practical choice for bridge projects [9].

Overall, bored cast-in-situ piles are an integral part of modern bridge construction. They provide a reliable foundation system that ensures the stability and longevity of the bridge structure [10]. With their versatility, strength, and cost-effectiveness, these piles continue to be a preferred choice for bridge engineers around the world.

Bored cast-in-situ piles are a popular choice for bridge foundations [11]. A larger diameter casing is used, and boring is carried out using a chisel while circulating bentonite slurry to stabilize the borehole. After reaching the desired founding level, a reinforcement cage is lowered, and concrete is poured using a tremie pipe [12].

Figure 2 bored cast-in-situ piles

III. METHOD OF STUDY

The study investigates a 100-meter by 16-meter RC road bridge with four spans of 25 meters each and four lanes of 4 meters width. Various pier heights ranging from 30 meters to 100 meters are considered, along with different pier configurations: Solid Circular, Double Circular with Tie, Double Circular with 2 Ties, and Double Circular without Tie. The analysis is carried out using STAAD software, considering seismic loading as the predominant lateral force.

TABLE-1 BRIDGE DETAILS

Parameter	Value
Deck Size	100m x 16m
Span Length	4 x 25m
Lane Width	4 x 4m
Pier Height	30m, 50m, 70m, 80m, 90m, 100m
Concrete Grade	M40, M50, M60, M70
Steel Grade	Fe415, Fe500

IV LOADS AND LOAD COMBINATIONS

The bridge is designed to withstand various loads and load combinations, as specified in the relevant codes and standards [13]. The loads considered in the analysis include dead load, live load (vehicle, impact, and braking), temperature load, and seismic load.

Dead Load

The self-weight of the structure is considered as the dead load, with a multiplying factor of 1.05 to account for any additional permanent loads.

Live Load

The live load comprises the weight of vehicles, impact loads, and braking forces. A multiplying factor of 0.20 is applied to account for these loads.

Temperature Load

Temperature variations can induce stresses in the bridge structure. A multiplying factor of 0.50 is used to account for temperature effects.

Additionally, seismic loads are considered, with a multiplying factor of +/- 1.5 to account for the horizontal and vertical components of earthquake forces.

V SEISMIC PERFORMANCE AND DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

The seismic performance of tall pier bridges is a critical aspect of the design process. The study emphasizes the importance of understanding the behavior of these structures under earthquake conditions and incorporating appropriate seismic design considerations.

Seismic Loading

The bridge must be designed to withstand seismic loads, which are typically the predominant lateral forces acting on tall pier bridges in seismic zones.

Structural Scheme

The structural scheme, including the pier configuration and cross-section, plays a crucial role in determining the seismic response of the bridge. The study evaluates various pier configurations to identify the most suitable options.

Advanced Analysis Techniques

Advanced analysis techniques, such as non-linear time-history analysis and 3D modeling, are essential for accurately predicting the behavior of tall pier bridges under seismic conditions.

By incorporating appropriate seismic design considerations and utilizing advanced analysis techniques, engineers can ensure the structural integrity and safety of tall pier bridges in earthquake-prone regions.

VI CONSTRUCTION TECHNIQUES AND CHALLENGES

The construction of tall pier bridges presents unique challenges that require specialized techniques and considerations. The study highlights some of the key aspects related to the construction of these structures.

Pier Construction

Tall piers are typically constructed using slip-form or jump-form techniques, which allow for continuous and efficient construction. Proper planning and execution of these methods are crucial to ensure quality and safety.

Foundation Construction

The construction of pile foundations for tall pier bridges requires specialized equipment and techniques, such as bored cast-in-situ piles or driven piles. Careful consideration must be given to factors like soil conditions, groundwater levels, and load transfer mechanisms.

Logistical Challenges

The construction of tall pier bridges in remote or challenging locations may require additional planning and logistical considerations, such as the transportation and handling of materials, site access, and temporary works.

By addressing these construction-related challenges and employing appropriate techniques, engineers and contractors can ensure the successful and efficient construction of tall pier bridges while maintaining safety and quality standards.

VII MAINTENANCE AND DURABILITY CONSIDERATIONS

The long-term performance and serviceability of tall pier bridges are heavily influenced by maintenance and durability considerations. The study highlights some of the key aspects related to these factors.

Inspection and Monitoring

Regular inspection and monitoring of the bridge structure, including the piers and foundations, are essential for identifying any potential issues or deterioration. Advanced techniques, such as structural health monitoring systems, can aid in this process.

Material Durability

The durability of construction materials, particularly concrete and reinforcement, plays a crucial role in the long-term performance of tall pier bridges. Appropriate material selection, quality control, and protection measures should be implemented.

Environmental Factors

Environmental factors, such as exposure to harsh weather conditions, aggressive chemicals, or seismic activity, can impact the durability of the bridge structure. Appropriate design measures and protective systems should be considered to mitigate these effects.

By implementing proper maintenance strategies and addressing durability concerns, engineers can extend the service life of tall pier bridges and ensure their long-term structural integrity and safety.

VIII CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis results and cost comparisons, the study provides recommendations for the optimum pier and foundation design for tall bridges.

Pier Height < 50m

For pier heights up to 50 meters, single solid circular piers, double circular piers with ties, and double circular piers with 2 ties are almost equally economical.

50m < Pier Height < 70m

Between 50 meters and 70 meters pier height, double circular piers with single and double ties are more economical than other pier types due to lower concrete consumption.

Pier Height > 70m

For pier heights above 70 meters, double circular piers with 2 ties become increasingly economical, especially when providing the minimum required pier diameter.

Regarding foundations, single solid piers are more economical up to 80 meters due to the minimum fixity depth and pile diameter requirements. Beyond 80 meters, double piers with ties and 2 ties prove more economical despite requiring two groups of pile foundations.

TOTAL COST

Total cost includes pier cost and pile foundation cost for every type of pier.

The total cost graph behaves similarly to the pier cost graph, up to 50 m height, Solid Single, Double (Tie + L/D), and Double (2 Tie + L/D) are almost equal but after 50 m height difference increases rapidly and Double (2 Tie + L/D) proves more and more economical as height increasing.

% COST CONTRIBUTION

All the charts of % cost contribution for all the types of piers show that as height increases % cost contribution of foundation decreases and also rate of decrement between 30 m to 50 m is too large, but then after % cost contribution of foundation becomes almost half and then after rate decrease.

% cost contribution of foundation cost for a Double pier having the same L/D Ratio is higher and for a Double pier having the same c/s Area is smaller as compared to a Single Solid pier.

IX FUTURE RESEARCH AND EMERGING TRENDS

The study of tall pier bridges is an ever-evolving field, with ongoing research and emerging trends shaping the future of bridge design and construction. Some areas of potential future research and trends include.

Advanced Materials

The development and application of advanced materials, such as high-performance concrete, fiber-reinforced composites, and innovative reinforcement systems, can lead to more durable and efficient tall pier bridge designs.

Sustainable Construction

Incorporating sustainable practices and materials in the construction of tall pier bridges can reduce the environmental impact and improve the overall sustainability of these structures.

Smart Monitoring Systems

The integration of smart monitoring systems, leveraging technologies like sensors, Internet of Things (IoT), and data analytics, can provide real-time structural health monitoring and enable proactive maintenance strategies.

Seismic Resilience

Ongoing research into seismic resilience and advanced seismic design techniques can improve the performance of tall pier bridges in earthquake-prone regions, enhancing public safety and minimizing post-event disruptions.

By staying abreast of the latest research and emerging trends, the civil engineering community can continue to push the boundaries of tall pier bridge design and construction, ensuring safer, more efficient, and more sustainable structures for the future.

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